

UKBOL Standard Operating Procedure: Dry Collection Sampling

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Specimen Selection

Specimens should be selected in consultation with the responsible curator, guided by a target species list. Where possible, aim to include three specimens per species, prioritising UK material in the first instance and supplementing with European specimens where necessary. Where both UK and European material is unavailable, it may be acceptable to supplement specimens from the near-Western Palaearctic. Any non-UK material must be checked to confirm that the country of origin has no ABS (Access and Benefit Sharing) or other legal restrictions on use – and the associated due diligence must be documented. All selected specimens should be in good physical condition with no visible fungal growth or evidence of collections pest activity, and preference should be given to expertly identified material from well-curated collections.

Each specimen should be placed into a size A unit tray labelled with its corresponding well number (e.g. A01) , and placed into a drawer labelled with the batch number. Since each batch will span across three drawers, the drawer sequence for that batch should also be included on the drawer label (e.g. UK010-1 to denote the first drawer of batch UK010). There are 96 wells and therefore 96 unit trays in each batch. Note that well H12 is a **control**, and **no specimen** should be placed in the corresponding unit tray.

Figure 1. Overview of specimens in their labelled unit trays, ready for processing.

Specimen Imaging

Different orders will need to be imaged from different angles (e.g. dorsal, lateral, ventral, taxonomically relevant detail close-up), so before imaging, consult with the relevant curators to determine which view(s) are relevant for the group(s) you are imaging.

Before you begin, it may be helpful to create a small 'stage' for your specimens using two rectangles of plastazote.

Using beetles as an example, which generally require dorsal and lateral photographs, the imaging process is outlined below:

1. Begin by attaching the camera to the camera mount, with the flash trigger attached.
2. Ensure the flashes are paired to the flash trigger
3. Pair your camera with your computer and open the relevant imaging software
4. Create a folder for your images and set this as the save destination within your imaging software
5. Take your first specimen (A01) from the drawer and place it on the plastazote as shown to take a dorsal image

6. Place your specimen under the lens, adjusting the height of the stand so that the specimen fills as much of the frame as possible
7. Click on your specimen in the software to autofocus, or adjust focus manually
8. Take image
9. Review image and if happy, right-click and select 'rename'. Use a barcode scanner to scan the barcode on the specimen and add "_dorsal" or "_lateral" depending on the image view (e.g. 016605963_dorsal.jpg)
10. Orientate the specimen on the plastazote as shown to take the lateral view
11. Repeat steps 7-10 for the lateral view.
12. Return specimen to its unit tray and return the tray to the drawer it came from
13. Repeat steps 6-13 for every specimen in the plate
14. Once finished check your saved images folder to ensure you have the correct number of images (190 for a plate - 95 dorsal and 95 lateral)
15. Upload your batch of images to SharePoint in a folder labelled with your batch number

Figure 2. Example dorsal and lateral voucher images.

Databasing

Label transcription

Label transcriptions should be captured into the CMS tab of the batch spreadsheet. Some fields are automatically filled in from data given in the Processing sheet. The spreadsheet is fairly self-explanatory, with defined fields for each type of data that may be included on specimen labels. However, some additional guidance is given below:

- Acquisition Number:
 - This refers to a code comprised of a year and an additional number in the format YYYY-#, where the year denotes the year that the specimen was obtained by the museum.
- Specimen Number (BMNHE)
 - A now defunct system of individual specimen numbers, which have been replaced by the use of NHMUK barcodes, comprises a 4-7 digit number, preceded by 'BMNHE'.
 - Specimens can possess both a specimen number and an NHMUK barcode.
- Series
 - Refers to the general location within the collection where the specimen is held.
 - Note that not all orders use a series system in their collections. In this case this field should be left blank and the entire locator should be entered in the 'Drawer' field.
- Determiner
 - The name of the person who identified the specimen to genus or species level.
 - The determiner may be the same or a different individual to the collector, or there may be no determiner given at all, in which case the field should be left blank.

- A specimen may possess more than one determination label. In this case, record only the name of the most contemporary determiner.
- If the identification is at odds with the position of the specimen in the collection, discuss the appropriate determiner name with the curator.
- Where only initials are given, it is helpful to expand these out as much as possible.
- Collector(s)
 - The name(s) of the person(s) who collected the specimen.
 - Where only initials are given, it is helpful to expand these out as much as possible, with the help of a curator if required.
- Dates
 - The date that the specimen was collected, if given.
 - Note that the month is frequently given in Roman numerals.
 - Some specimens provide a date range for when they were collected, for example 3-6/v/2024. In this case, Day2/Month2/Year2 ('end date') should be filled in, in addition to Day/Month/Year ('start date'), in the following format:

Day	Month	Year	Day2	Month2	Year2
3	5	2024	6	5	2024

- Some specimens provide only a year or year and month of collection. In these cases, both Day/Month/Year ('start date') and Day2/Month2/Year2 ('end date') should be filled in, beginning on the first day of year/month and ending on the last day of the year/month given. For example, a date given simply as '2024' should be transcribed in the following format:

Day	Month	Year	Day2	Month2	Year2
1	1	2024	31	12	2024

- Notes
 - Additional data, for which no specific field is provided and that may be of use, can be transcribed here. Examples include method of collection (e.g. 'vane trap'), substrate in which the specimen was found (e.g. 'in moss') or habitat type (e.g. 'heathland').
- Verbatim Site Data
 - The exact locality of collection.
 - This field should exclude any details given regarding substrate or general habitat type (see 'Note for EMu Record' above).

- Whilst this data should generally be transcribed verbatim, obvious abbreviations can be expanded out (e.g. 'R. Tweed' for 'River Tweed', or 'N. Stifford' for 'North Stifford').
- Localities given in other languages and/or archaic terms can be clarified with square brackets.

Georeferencing

All coordinates should be found through direct information found on existing specimen labels. When provided as Post Code, Addresses, Grid References, Easting and Northing, they should be transformed into decimal Latitude and Longitude using a service such as <https://gridreferencefinder.com/>. In cases where data is limited, the latitude and longitude are to be estimated using a map service, for example Google Earth, to find the general area described on the label, and use the following coordinate precision:

- .1 = somewhere within 10km of the location described
- .01 = 1km of the location described
- .001 = 100m of the location described

In cases where there is ambiguous or insufficient data (e.g. the locality cannot be located/interpreted or only a country is given) the latitude and longitude may be left blank.

BOLD data upload

Metadata of each UKBOL voucher specimen, including taxonomic identity, collection information, and additional data must be compiled into a BOLD processing sheet template and submitted to BOLD Systems. See the **BOLD specimen upload SOP** for detailed guidance on the preparation of specimen metadata in a spreadsheet and its subsequent upload through the BOLD Systems v.5 website.

BOLD image upload

Images of voucher specimens corresponding to the metadata must be uploaded to BOLD Systems. This process involves the automated population of an image metadata template provided by BOLD using an Office script in MS Excel. The images files are then resized using XNConvert and packaged alongside the spreadsheet into a zip file, ready for upload through the BOLD Systems website. See the **BOLD image upload SOP** for detailed guidance.

Tissue Sampling

Materials needed:

- Dissecting microscope
- Deionised water
- Fine forceps (preferably no.5)
- Fine paintbrushes
- Pins of varying sizes
- Pipettes for deionised water
- Disposable gloves
- Bead heater (set to 250°C)
- Container with 10% bleach solution

BEFORE SAMPLING:

- All surfaces, equipment and tools should be sterilised before any form of tissue extraction is undertaken to avoid contamination of tissue samples.
- PPE such as a lab coat and disposable gloves should be worn.
- To sterilise surfaces, spray with a solution of 10% bleach before wiping down with dry tissue.
- To sufficiently sterilise the forceps, they should first be soaked for 5-10 minutes in a solution of 10% bleach, then rinsed thoroughly with distilled water before being placed into a bead heater that has been preheated to 250°C for a minimum of 5 minutes. It is most efficient to sterilise enough forceps for at least one column before initiating the sampling process. Once the column is complete, they can then be resterilised.
- To sterilise paintbrushes, soak in a solution of 10% bleach for at least 5 minutes before rinsing thoroughly with distilled water, paying close attention to any tissue on the bristles.

EXTRACTION OF TISSUE:

1. Take the first column of specimens to be sampled (A01-H01) and line them up in this order near to the microscope.
2. Take first column of 8-strip tubes (pre-labelled with corresponding well numbers, e.g. A01, B01, C01...) pre-filled with lysis buffer from the tube rack in the fridge and transfer them into a second tube rack in close proximity to the microscope.
3. Take the first specimen to be sampled and place under the microscope. Note that depending on the type of insect being sampled, it may be suitable or necessary to extract different tissues. For larger specimens, a single leg may be sufficient, whereas smaller specimens may need both a leg and the abdomen to be sampled. In the case of very small insects, some orders, such as Coleoptera, are suitable for whole specimen sampling.
4. Take a pair of sterilised forceps and carefully remove the desired tissue from the specimen under the microscope.

5. Place this tissue into the lysis buffer in the corresponding tube. Make certain that all the tissue sampled is fully submerged in the lysis buffer; small legs can often adhere to the sides of the tube, and legs of larger specimens may need to be carefully folded at the joints to ensure they are fully submerged. Once complete close the lid of the tube to prevent accidental contamination with tissue from subsequent specimens.
6. Place the used forceps and any other tools such as paintbrushes into the container of 10% bleach solution. Each tool used must only be used to extract tissue from one specimen and must be completely resterilised before they are used again.
7. Repeat for subsequent specimens in the column.
8. Place the unit trays back in the drawer. Make sure the lids of the lysis buffer tubes are properly closed and return this to the tube rack containing the other columns of strip tubes in the fridge.
9. Change your gloves.
10. Repeat with the remaining columns until the entire batch has been sampled.

Depending on the specimen and specific tissues to be sampled, the equipment and technique used will vary. For example, pins can be helpful when sampling carded specimens. Whole specimens may need to be soaked off point or card mounts using deionised water; for this process, pipettes and paintbrushes are highly recommended.

Tissue Recovery

Before initiating tissue recovery, the binding buffer plate wells and pipette tips need to be assessed for any possible insect tissue lost in the DNA extraction procedure. A member of the lab team will supply the relevant batch, with pipette tips matched to their corresponding trays. Once examined, these can be disposed of according to standard lab procedures. If tissue remains are identified at this stage, immerse them in 70% ethanol and place them back into their respective tube.

Discuss with the curator the requirements for each taxonomic group, as specifics of tissue repatriation may vary between each taxon. Generally, the tissue will either be reattached to the specimen, mounted on the card beside the specimen, or preserved within a gelatine capsule and attached to the pin.

Upon receiving the tissue samples, they will be found preserved in 70% ethanol within their respective batch number of labelled tubes from A01 to H12.

Reattaching tissue is not a standardised procedure due to variation between each specimen and taxonomic group. However, some general points of consideration are provided here:

- Using a fine paintbrush is ideal for the transposition of delicate tissue. Once soaked in ethanol, the tissue clings to the bristles and this method can be used to take the samples out of the lysis tube without damaging them, or to rearrange tissues on a card
- Use a glue appropriate to the specimen and task at hand provided by the relevant curator.

- Depending on preference, a fine paintbrush or a pin dabbed in the glue can be used to apply the adhesive to the specimen. If a paintbrush is used, ensure it is cleaned in a small amount of ethanol after each use to prevent build-up or hardening of the bristles.
- A set up which allows for ventral orientation of the specimen may be helpful when reattaching tissues to pinned specimens. This can be achieved by creating a small ‘stage’ from rectangles of plastazote.
- When using gelatine capsules, ensure the tissue is dry so the capsule does not dissolve.

Specimen Labelling

Once DNA extracts are archived in appropriate tubes in the NHM Biobank the relevant data is added to the specimen. Labels include the project name, the BOLD Process ID, the BOLD Sample ID which is typically formed of batch code and corresponding well position (e.g. UK001-A01) and the DNA tube barcode (Figure 3).

UKBOL voucher BOLD: DEFRA191-26 ID: UK001-A01 DNA tube: FA15132080

Figure 3. Example specimen label.

Specimen Return

Once the sequence data has been analysed and verified the repaired and labelled specimen can be returned to the collection.